

A Sensor-Based Technologized Application for the Construction of a Wireless Smart Bridge

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ABSTRACT: In this work, an enhancement for the security of the bridge is carried out by a wireless technique with the use of a bend sensor has been introduced. This microcontroller based technique overcomes the drawbacks of various types of wired security used all over the world. The main aim is to check the health of the bridge and monitoring the security due to heavy vehicles, to prevent accidents [1]. The strength of the bridge decreases as a consequence bridge which undergoes structural damagedue to daily wear and tear. This can be lead to a major accident [2]. To measure the amount of bend subjected to bridges, we are using a Bend Sensor which will produce an analog electrical signal proportional to bend experienced by the bridge which changes in a convex or concave shape. This analog voltage which is directly proportional to the bend is amplified by non-inverting amplifier converted in digital form by ADC and encoded by an encoder and send towards RF transmitter which is received by RF transmitter and decoded if the generated voltage is greater than predefine voltage beyond a safety limit of bend our system will activate the alarm otherwise keep on displaying bend value on LCD [3-4]. To prevent any accident we are implementing a miniature model that will continuously monitor the health of the bridge [5]. The advantage of this project is easily operated in which the bridge is directly controlled by buzzer which works at a far distance from the control room based on microcontroller-based programming [6]. The objective of this paper is to fill a need concerning the strategy for utility or utilization of bend sensors [14-15].

KEYWORDS: Bend Sensor, Microcontroller (AT89C52), ADC (PIC16LF77), RF Transmitter/Receiver, Decoder (HT12D), Buzzer.

I. INTRODUCTION

To ensure the security of the health monitoring of bridge we used wire communication from the transmitter to the receiver which may costly and difficult to handle [7-8]. The preparation of SHM systems to large-scale civil infrastructure systems guarantees to notice and track structural degradation in real-time and an inexpensive manner. [9]. However, the native characteristics of degradation (e.g., corrosion, cracking) need a heavy network of sensors to be spatially distributed with in the structure [15]. The bounded communications systems have been employed by structural monitoring systems for the decades. As the wiring demands for the large infrastructure systems are high (e.g., the installation of kilometers of wires), hence it will result in a very costly and high delayed installations in an unfortunate manner. [6, 10]. But this problem can be overcome by emerging wireless sensors as a possible alternative to the wired sensors. The conclusions we found out during this study were autonomous and strictly designated to scale. The main objective of this work is to make a device that works for the safety of the bridge through the bend sensor which will minimize the accidents occurs due to bridges, measure the health of bridges, control the bridge's health and control the overload on the bridge. The monitoring system has so many advantages. Such as-

Reliability: The device which is used is very simple and reliable because it is a wireless bridge health monitoring. Since the hardware used is very simple and noise-free and for transmission radiofrequency is used.

Scalability: The output voltage generated by the bend sensor is in analog form and it is changed by analog to digital converter so the resolution is high.

Flexibility: The design is such that it can be put to use in various systems, with different requirements and mechanisms.

II. COMPONENTS USED IN THE CONSTRUCTION OF WIRELESS SMART BRIDGE

In this work, various components have been used for the designing and monitoring of wireless smart bridges which helps in the functioning of the system in full advance technologized manner. For a clear explanation, this section is further divided into different subsections.

A. Bend Sensor

A bend sensor for measuring a deflection of a technical or medical instrument, consisting of an elongated body of electrically insulating polymer material, with a longitudinal axis and with fibers of an electrically conducting polymer material that are embedded in the body [3]. The fibers are disposed essentially parallel to the longitudinal axis and at a distance from one another in the polymer body. A measuring unit is connected with the fibers and is suited for evaluating the modification of the electrical resistance of the fibers as a measurement of the deflection of the body from the longitudinal axis [11]. The bend sensor is made of tiny patches of carbon that manipulate resistance values when bent from convex to concave shapes. The bend sensor is used jointly with a potential divider to provide changing voltages.

Fig 1: Bend Sensor of bend sensor when the bend

Fig. 2: Variation of resistance when the bend is in either direction

Bend Sensor Characteristic: Bi-Directional Flexible Bend sensor based on their bending quality. Its resistance varies with respect to bend created by the bend sensor. It's nominal resistance of 10 KΩ which decreases when the sensor is bent in either direction.

Circuit Working: The circuit of the bend sensor is mainly divided into two parts

- Transmitting panel
- Receiving panel

Figure 3 given below shows the components at the transmitting and receiving panel.

Figure 3

Figure 3-Components at Transmitting and receiving panel

Figure 4(a) and (b) shows the transmitting and receiving panels.

Fig4-a) Transmitting Panel of Monitoring System

Fig4-b) Receiving Panel of Monitoring System

Transmitting pannel transmit the signal and it will send to receiving panel (control room) where if the generated voltage is greater then predefine voltage then the buzzer will work otherwise it will display on LCD screen[1]. Due to the wireless transmission effect of noise is less and least costly.

Figure: 5(a) Transmitting Panel Circuit Diagram

Figure:5(b) Receiving Panel Circuit Diagram

B. Amplifier LM358 IC

Since the intensity of the signal produced by the bend sensor is weak which is in the range of 5 to 6 mv, so the non- inverting amplifier is used to amplify its magnitude in the same phase. Figure 6 given below shows the amplifier has been used to amplify the output of the bend sensor [13].

Figure 6: Use of the amplifier to amplify the output of the bend sensor. [3]

The amplifier LM358IC is an integrated circuit that consists of a set of various electrical and electronic components like resistors, capacitors, transistors, etc. All these components are integrated onto a single chip. It's available in an 8-pin DIP package. Here I used for amplification of voltage generated through the bend sensor [15]. The LM358 IC amplifier has features like wide bandwidth of 1MHz, large voltage gain and large operating range. It has also very low supply current drain and offset voltage with a large voltage swing. The pin diagram of LM358 IC comprises of 8 pins where pin-1 and pin-7 are o/p of the comparator, pin-2 and pin-6 are inverting inputs, pin-3 and pin-5 are non-inverting inputs, pin-4 is GND terminal and pin-8 is V_{CC} .

Figure 7: Pin diagram of LM358 IC [16]

C. Signal Conditioning

In electronics, the manipulation of the analog signal is carried out in the signal conditioning process in a precise manner so that it can be used for the next stage that is the conversation of this analog signal to digital form by using Analog-to-Digital converters [4]. In control engineering applications, the common stages are sensing stage, signal conditioning stage, processing stage (which normally carried out by microcontroller and ADC)[3]. The amplification of the signal is carried out by the Op-Amp in this signal conditioning stage.

D. PIC16F877A Microcontroller (ADC)

PIC16F877 is a class of 8-bit microcontrollers which comes under RISC architecture. It consists of a flash memory of 8 KB for storing program data. [14]. Since the memory is made up of flash technology; hence it can be programmed and cleared more than once and can make this microcontroller very suitable for the development of the device. But the data memory needs to be saved in the absence of supply so that the stored data must not be lost if the power supply suddenly terminated. If accidentally the data will be lost during the loss of power supply, then again the data will be adjusted when power supply comes.

The main parts of PIC16F877A are 10-bit Analog-to-Digital converter (8 channels), self-programming, an ICD, EEPROM data memory (256 bytes) and two Comparators [16].

Figure 8: PIC16F877A Microcontroller

E. HT12E Encoder

The operation voltage range of HT12E is from 2.4V to 12V. It contains a built-in oscillator which requires only a small value of the external resistor. It has very less power consumption with a standby current of 0.1µA at $V_{DD} = 5V$ and is less sensitive to noise. It is available in 18 pin DIP (Dual Inline Package) and 20 pin SOP (Small Outline Package) as given below [10].

Figure 9: HT12E Encoder Pin Diagram

F. PIC (AT89C52) Microcontroller

The PIC AT89C52 is a highly performable Complementary MOS structured 8-bit microcontroller with Flash Programmable and Erasable Read-Only Memory (PEROM) of 8 KB. It also need very low power supply

G. RF Transmitter and Receiver

This section will modulate the incoming digital signal in the RF range. After then it will transmit a signal in the form of electromagnetic waves. The RF receiver will receive the desire RF signal. After that it will demodulate the RF signal.

H. Decoder (HT-12D):

It acts as a signal conditioning section which will convert the input signal into a form that can be understood by the microcontroller. Microcontroller will analyze incoming data and compare it with the limiting bend value. If the bend value exceeds limiting value, the microcontroller will turn on the alarm [12]. This decoder, which undoing the encoding helps in original information retrieve [12]. In digital electronics, the decoder can take multiple coded inputs and can convert these coded inputs into coded outputs, where both the input and output codes are different. During the operation of decoder, the output assumes to be a single “disabled” output coded word if the enable inputs will not “ON”. In many applications like memory address decoding, seven-segment displays, multiplexing of data, the decoding is required.

I. Buzzer and LCD

A buzzer produces small beep sound is simply an audio signaling device which can be an electromechanical or piezoelectric or simply mechanical by property. The buzzers are used in timer circuit, alarm, mobile, vehicles etc [16]. The LCD is an electronic visual or flat panel or video display which does not emit light directly [1]. It uses the light modulating properties of liquid crystals. LCD is used to display random images just like as general-purpose computer display or LCD can also display mounted images that can be hidden or display.

J. Speaker

Speakers vary staggeringly in size and form. They will be designed as crystal or electrical phenomenon, however, most frequently they are dynamic (called electro-dynamic construction). The 2 most significant characteristics of a speaker are its resistance (As the resistance of the speaker is determined at a frequency of 1 kHz, and so its value is higher than the actual resistance hence it's generally called as speaker impedance) and its power. Some common values of impedance are 4, 8, 16Ω; however 1.5, 40, and 80Ω speakers can also be made.

K. Power Supply

We used to give power supply from AC to DC through the given circuit.

Figure 10:DC Power Supply for the Monitoring System

III. LIMITATION

Though several precautions have been taken in order to design this wireless monitoring system, still it produces few limitations even after using advanced technologized applications. Some of the limitations are

1. It will monitor up to a certain range of tilt due to heavy vehicles
2. It is not able to monitor bridge health before the arrival of heavy vehicles.
3. It is for small level monitoring of bridge health.
4. The result may be affected by the change of weather.

IV. CONCLUSION

Based on the design, principles and requirement, a prototype of the system for bridge health monitoring system has been developed using bend sensor which works on the programming of microcontroller. It is much more advanced than wired security system. It will help in minimize dangerous accident due to overloaded vehicles and hence can save from the severe damages of nation's properties. Human lives are valuable, full up of emotions and strong attachments with each other. Saving lives, by saving accidents and by saving properties can lead to several benefits in several manners and also can save earth atmosphere in the direct and indirect way.

Figure 11: Whole Setup of wireless bridge health monitoring system

V. FUTURE SCOPE OF THIS WORK

As this monitoring system is designed by advanced technologized microcontrollers and wireless-based sensors, so no doubt it is very helpful for controlling unfortunate and unwanted losses and it is obvious also. But simultaneously it has few limitations also which has already stated above. So in the future, further work can be processed for increasing the range of tilt so that prior conscious can be made. This may be possible by increasing the sensing capacity of the bend sensor in any way. Again the accuracy level of bridge monitoring can be improved by certain changes in design. The most important limitation is the system sensitiveness towards weather changes and this makes the entire system less adorable. So in the future, the main focus is to make a replacement of a few components used in the system to reduce the sensitiveness towards weather changes.

REFERENCES

1. N. A. J. Lieven, D. J. Ewins, Charles R. Farrar, Scott W. Doebling and David A. Nix (2001) "Vibration-based structural damage identification", *Phil. Trans. R. Soc. A*.359131–149
2. Khadersab, A., &Shivakumar, S. (2018). Vibration analysis techniques for rotating machinery and its effect on bearing faults. *Procedia Manufacturing*, 20, 247-252.
3. Alan V. Oppenheim, and Ronald W. Schafer "Digital Signal Processing" Prentice Hall international editionsProceedings of the IEEE, April 1975. Vol. 63:4
4. Boashash, B. (2015). *Time-frequency signal analysis and processing: a comprehensive reference*. Academic Press.
5. Tennyson, R. C., & Morison, D. (2006, March). Long gage-length fiber optic sensors for monitoring pipeline integrity. In *Smart Structures and Materials 2006: Smart Sensor Monitoring Systems and Applications* (Vol. 6167, p. 61671C). International Society for Optics and Photonics.
6. Farrar, C. R., Doebling, S. W., & Nix, D. A. (2001). Vibration-based structural damage identification. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society of London. Series A: Mathematical, Physical and Engineering Sciences*, 359(1778), 131-149.
7. Williams, N. W. (1997). The virtual hand: The Pulvertaft prize essay for 1996. *Journal of Hand Surgery*, 22(5), 560-567.
8. Williams, N. W., Penrose, J. M. T., Caddy, C. M., Barnes, E., Hose, D. R., & Harley, P. (2000). A goniometric glove for clinical hand assessment: construction, calibration and validation. *The Journal of Hand Surgery: British & European Volume*, 25(2), 200-207.
9. Dipietro, L., Sabatini, A. M., & Dario, P. (2003). Evaluation of an instrumented glove for hand-movement acquisition. *Journal of rehabilitation research and development*, 40(2), 179-190.
10. Papakostas, T. V., & White, N. M. (2000). Influence of substrate on the gauge factor of polymer thick-film resistors. *Journal of Physics D: Applied Physics*, 33(14), L73.
11. Williams, R. (1963). Domains in liquid crystals. *The Journal of Chemical Physics*, 39(2), 384-388.
12. Scheffer, T. J., &Nehring, J. (1984). A new, highly multiplexable liquid crystal display. *Applied Physics Letters*, 45(10), 1021-1023.
13. Dipietro, L., Sabatini, A. M., & Dario, P. (2008). A survey of glove-based systems and their applications. *IEEE Transactions on Systems, Man, and Cybernetics, Part C (Applications and Reviews)*, 38(4), 461-482.
14. Sohn, Hoon; Farrar, Charles R.; Hemez, Francois M.; Shunk, Devin D.; Stinemates, Daniel W.; Nadler, Brett R.; Czarneci, Jerry J. (2004). *A Review of Structural Health Monitoring Literature: 1996–2001*. Los Alamos, NM: Los Alamos National Laboratories. Retrieved 2010-07-10.
15. Worden, Keith; Charles R. Farrar, Graeme Manson and Gyuhae Park (2007). "The Fundamental Axioms of Structural Health Monitoring". *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society: Mathematical, Physical & Engineering Sciences* 463 (2082):1639–1664. doi:10.1098/rspa.2007.1834.
16. Sedra, A. S., Sedra, D. E. A. S., Smith, K. C., & Smith, K. C. (1998). *Microelectronic circuits*. New York: Oxford University Press.